

Journal of Pure and Applied
Ultrasonics

Website : www.ultrasonicsindia.org

A Publication of Ultrasonics Society of India

Temperature dependent ultrasonic characterization of AuRE intermetallics

Mohd Aftab Khan^{1*}, Chandreshvar Prasad Yadav¹, Mahendra Kumar^{1,2},
Dharmendra Kumar Pandey¹, Devendra Nath Mishra³ and Renuka Arora¹

¹Department of Physics, P.P.N. (P.G.) College, Kanpur, Uttar Pradesh-208 001, India

²Department of Physics, D.B.S. (P.G.) College, Kanpur, Uttar Pradesh-208 006, India

³Department of Physics, United College of Engineering & Research, Naini, Prayagraj, Uttar Pradesh-211 010, India

*E-mail: aftab1516@gmail.com

The present work incorporates computation of elastic, ultrasonic and thermal properties of B2 structured AuRE (RE= Sm, Tb, Ho, Tm) intermetallics in temperature range 300K-900K. Initially, elastic constants are determined under potential model approach. Later on, ultrasonic velocities are obtained in the same temperature range for wave propagation along $\langle 100 \rangle$ and $\langle 111 \rangle$ crystallographic directions. Besides it, Debye temperatures, thermal energy density, thermal expansion coefficient and melting temperature are also determined for chosen intermetallics. The obtained results are compared and analyzed to explore the inherent properties the chosen material.

Keywords: Rare-earth intermetallics; elastic properties; ultrasonic velocity; thermo-physical properties.

Introduction

Intermetallics are homogeneous and composite materials comprising of two or more types of metal atoms that differ in structure in comparison to their constituent metals. Binary rare-earth intermetallic compounds have many practical applications due to their superior mechanical, thermo-dynamical, electrical and magnetic properties in comparison to ordinary metals. These materials possess high strength, ductility, melting point, good corrosion resistance and low specific heat which make them important for aerospace and commercial aircraft turbines applications. Rare-earth intermetallics exhibit B2 type CsCl structure. The rare earth elements have electron occupancy in f-shell with a regular change in atomic dimension and electro-negativity on moving along rare-earth group¹⁻⁶.

The study of binary rare earth intermetallics represents an important part of the metallic phases⁷. The ab-initio and First principle studies of rare earth intermetallics monoaurides (Ln-Au) and Lanthenide-Gold (R-Au) respectively have been done by Sardar Ahmad and his co-workers^{1, 8} to examine the electronic and magnetic properties of the materials. The thermodynamic assessment of Au-Ho and Au-Tm binary systems have

been reported in literature⁷ using the CALPHAD (Calculation of Phase Diagrams) method. The experimental study of Au, Ag, Cu and Al based rare-earth intermetallic compounds are reported elsewhere^{2, 7}. The survey of literatures indicate that, in spite of technological importance of these rare earth intermetallic, a systematic theoretical study of structural, elastic, ultrasonic and thermo-physical properties of these materials, is still needed for future applications. The present work is focused on characterization of elastic, ultrasonic and thermo-physical properties of AuRE (RE= Sm, Tb, Ho, Tm) intermetallic at different temperature. The temperature dependent second order elastic constants (SOECs) and elastic moduli (bulk modulus- B , Young's modulus- Y , shear modulus- G , Lamé modulus- λ & μ and Poisson's ratio- σ) of chosen binary intermetallics have initially been determined using potential model approach considering interaction up to second nearest neighbors. Subsequently, the ultrasonic velocities for wave propagation along two crystallographic directions ($\langle 100 \rangle$ and $\langle 111 \rangle$) and thermo-physical properties (Debye temperature, thermal energy density, thermal expansion coefficient and melting temperature) are also determined at same physical conditions.

Theory

Theory of elastic constants

The elastic constants of B2/CsCl structured materials have been evaluated on the basis of only two basic parameters (lattice and non-linear parameters) using potential model approach. Under this model, second order elastic constants are determined by the second order differentiation of elastic energy density with respect to strain while elastic energy density is attained by considering interaction among atoms defined by Coulomb and Born-Mayer interaction potentials assuming interaction up to second nearest neighbours with respect to reference atom.

According to Hooke's law, stress is directly proportional to strain under small deformation. The generalized form of this law can be written as:

$$X_I = \sum_{I,J=1,\dots,6} C_{IJ} \eta_J \quad (1)$$

Where, X_I and η_J are the components of stress and strain tensor, respectively. The term C_{IJ} is called as coefficient of elastic constants. The elastic energy density (F) of undeformed crystal is function of these components of strain tensor ($\eta_j; j=1,\dots,6$)⁹.

$$F = (\eta_1, \eta_2, \eta_3, \eta_4, \eta_5, \eta_6) \quad (2)$$

Therefore, the elastic energy density (F) can be expanded in terms of strain using Taylor's series expansion as:

(3)

The strain derivative of elastic energy density provides the elastic constant of the material. Therefore, the second order elastic constants are defined as:

$$C_{IJ} = \frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial \eta_I \partial \eta_J}; \quad I \text{ or } J = 1, 2, \dots, 6 \quad (4)$$

The expansion of elastic energy density (F) in terms of strain is defined by Eq.(3). Using this expression, the free energy density in square terms of strain can be written as:

$$F_2 = \frac{1}{2!} C_{IJ} \eta_I \eta_J \quad (5)$$

The tensor form relationship between stress and strain gives 36 types of SOECs or stiffness constants. Under the symmetry condition of cubic B2 structured material, these stiffness constants (C_{IJ}) reduce to only three types

as C_{11} , C_{12} and C_{44} while rest becomes zero¹⁰. Therefore, the extension of Eq. (5), under symmetry condition of B2 structured materials takes the following form:

$$F_2 = (1/2) \left[C_{11} (\eta_1^2 + \eta_2^2 + \eta_3^2) + C_{12} (\eta_1 \eta_2 + \eta_1 \eta_3 + \eta_2 \eta_3) + 2C_{44} (\eta_4^2 + \eta_5^2 + \eta_6^2) \right] \quad (6)$$

The elastic energy density (F) at finite temperature (T) is sum of energy density at 0K (F^0) and increase in energy (vibrational part of energy density: F^V) with enhancement in temperature by amount T ¹¹.

$$F = F^0 + F^V \quad (7)$$

Therefore, Eq. (4) has the following form.

$$C_{IJ} = \frac{\partial^2 F^0}{\partial \eta_I \partial \eta_J} + \frac{\partial^2 F^V}{\partial \eta_I \partial \eta_J} \quad (8)$$

The first part in R.H.S of Eq. (8) is termed as static part of SOECs (C_{IJ}^0) which have a constant value while second part varies with temperature because vibrational free energy density depends on temperature recognized as vibrational parts of SOECs (C_{IJ}^V). Hence, the expression of SOECs at finite temperature T becomes as:

$$C_{IJ} = C_{IJ}^0 + C_{IJ}^V \quad (9)$$

The static and vibrational part of SOECs (C_{IJ}^0 & C_{IJ}^V) can be computed with the expressions given in our previous work¹¹⁻¹⁶. The estimation of second order elastic constants requires only lattice and non-linear parameters as an input under this potential model approach. The second order elastic constants can be utilized for the evaluation of bulk modulus (B), Shear modulus (G), Young's modulus (Y), Lamé modulus (λ , μ) and Poisson ratio (σ) as reported in literature^{12,17}.

Theory of ultrasonic velocity

When an ultrasonic waves propagates in the medium, there are three types of ultrasonic velocities for each direction of propagation in cubic crystals, one is longitudinal velocity (V_L) and other two are shear velocities (V_{S1} and V_{S2}), which can be estimated with following expressions for the wave propagation along $\langle 100 \rangle$ and $\langle 111 \rangle$ crystallographic directions^{12, 18}.

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \text{along } \langle 100 \rangle : V_L &= \sqrt{C_{11}/d} & ; V_S &= \sqrt{C_{44}/d} \\ \text{along } \langle 111 \rangle : V_L &= \sqrt{(C_{11} + 2C_{12} + 4C_{44})/3d} & ; V_S &= \sqrt{(C_{11} - C_{12} + 2C_{44})/3d} \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (10)$$

The density of CsCl/B2 structured material can be determined with the expression given in literature¹⁹. Debye average velocity is an important parameter in the

low temperature physics because it is related to elastic constants through ultrasonic velocities. The Debye average velocity (V_D) is defined as given in equation¹⁸.

$$V_D = \left[\frac{1}{3} \left(\frac{1}{V_L^3} + \frac{2}{V_S^3} \right) \right]^{-1/3} \quad (11)$$

On the basis of evaluated second order elastic constants, the ultrasonic velocities of the material also have been calculated.

Thermo-physical Properties

The temperature corresponding to maximum frequency of phonon that can propagate through crystalline media is termed as Debye temperature. The Debye temperature (TD) is indirectly related to elastic constants through Debye average velocity¹⁸.

$$T_D = \frac{hV_D (6 \pi^2 n_a)^{1/3}}{2\pi k_B} \quad (12)$$

Here, h is Planck's constant and n_a is atom concentration.

The thermal expansion behavior of material can be described on the knowledge of thermal expansion coefficient (α) and melting point (M_p). The variation in density/volume of crystalline material is caused by alteration in lattice parameter with temperature/pressure. The reduction in density or enhancement in volume of crystalline medium with increase in temperature leads the following expression of linear thermal expansion

coefficient¹⁴⁻¹⁶.

$$\alpha = \frac{V - V_0}{3 T V_0} = \frac{d_0 - d}{3 T d} \quad (13)$$

Here, d_0 and V_0 are density and volume at 0K. The thermal expansion coefficient can be determined using Eq. (13) on the knowledge of temperature dependent density. The melting temperature (M_p) of the CsCl structured intermetallic compounds are well related to the thermal expansion coefficient and is equal to $0.38(\alpha + 7.0 \times 10^{-6})^{-1}$,¹⁴

Results and Discussion

The temperature dependent lattice parameters (a) of chosen AuRE intermetallics are calculated with help of formulation given in literature¹⁴ and using corresponding room temperature lattice parameters^{1, 8}. The molecular weight of AuSm, AuTb, AuHo and AuTm intermetallics are 347.33 gm, 355.89 gm, 361.90 gm and 365.90 gm, respectively. The non-linearity parameters (b) of AuSm, AuTb, AuHo and AuTm intermetallics are determined under equilibrium condition and are found 0.798 Å, 0.721 Å, 0.663 Å and 0.381 Å, respectively. The calculated lattice parameters and molecular weights are utilized for the estimation of the densities at different temperatures for the chosen intermetallics using the expression given in literature^{12, 19}. Both the calculated temperature dependent lattice parameters and densities are given in Table 1.

Table 1 – Basic parameters lattice parameters (a), non-linear parameters (b), Molecular weight (M_w) and density (d) of AuRE compounds.

AuRE→		AuSm	AuTb	AuHo	AuTm
Parameters↓	T[K]				
a (Å)					
	300K	3.621	3.576	3.541	3.516
	450K	3.633	3.588	3.553	3.526
	600K	3.646	3.600	3.565	3.536
	750K	3.659	3.613	3.577	3.547
	900K	3.672	3.625	3.589	3.557
b (Å)					
		0.798	0.721	0.663	0.381
M_w (gm)					
		347.33	355.89	361.90	365.90
d (gm cm ⁻³)					
	300K	12.14	12.92	13.53	13.97
	450K	12.02	12.78	13.39	13.85
	600K	11.89	12.65	13.26	13.73
	750K	11.76	12.52	13.13	13.61
	900K	11.64	12.39	12.96	13.49

Fig. 1. Thermal expansion coefficient (α) and melting point vs. AuRE intermetallics

Thermal expansion coefficient and melting temperature of selected intermetallics are estimated with the help of Eq. (13) and are shown in Fig. 1.

The lattice parameters of selected intermetallics have been found to enhance with temperature and decay with materials which are received to be maximum for AuSm while minimum for AuTm intermetallic (Table 1). The similar nature of lattice parameters of AgRE intermetallics with temperature have also been reported in literature¹⁶. The increase in lattice parameter is due to enhancement in average inter-atomic distance caused by increase in thermal/lattice vibration energy. The low value of lattice parameter confirms the high inter-atomic forces; therefore the material AuTm will have higher inter-atomic strength than AuSm intermetallic. Since, the selected intermetallics are B2 structured materials whose densities vary inversely to be third power of lattice parameter, hence the density of selected intermetallics has been found to enhance from AuSm to AuTm while received to decay with temperature. The calculated density of AuTb, AuHo and AuTm are similar to reported literature values at 300K¹. The electronic configuration of Au, Sm, Tb, Ho and Tm are $[\text{Xe}]4f^{14}5d^{10}6s^1$, $[\text{Xe}]4f^{66}6s^2$, $[\text{Xe}]4f^{11}6s^2$ and $[\text{Xe}]4f^{13}6s^2$, respectively. The configuration reveals that Au possesses half filled s-sub shell while the vacancy of f-sub shell saturates from Sm to Tm. Therefore, Au with Tm will form more stable intermetallics having strong inter-atomic bond strength in comparison to intermetallics formed with Sm. The maximum change in lattice parameter of AuSm, AuTb, AuHo and AuTm for temperature variation of 600K has been received

1.41%, 1.37%, 1.35% and 1.17% respectively. In the similar way, the density has been found to decay by 4.12%, 4.10%, 4.21% and 3.44% respectively. The low percentage change in lattice parameter and density with temperature of AuTm with respect to other selected intermetallics confirms its strong inter-atomic bond strength.

The evaluated second order elastic constants and elastic moduli B , G , Y , σ , λ and μ are evaluated using estimated lattice parameters and is depicted in Table 2 under variation of temperature range 300-900 K for selected intermetallics. The second order elastic constants, bulk modulus, Young's modulus, shear modulus, Lamé module and Poisson's ratio of the AuSm to AuTm at 300K are approximately same as given in literature¹. Thus, present second order elastic constants and elastic moduli of chosen compounds under potential model approach are justified. Since, our potential model approach for evaluation of second order elastic constants needs only lattice parameter and provides good results, it is therefore, better than other models. Since, the interatomic bonding strength for AuRE intermetallic enhances as RE changes from Sm to Tm, therefore elastic moduli of AuRE intermetallics are found to increase from AuSm to AuTm (Table 2).

The temperature dependent SOECs are very important for understanding the mechanical strength, stability and phase transition of material under effect of temperature. The SOECs C_{11} and C_{12} of AuRE decrease with increase in temperature while C_{44} increases with enhancement in temperature. Since, the lattice parameters are found to enhance with temperature therefore, interaction force among atoms will reduce with temperature. This is the reason behind the decay of C_{11} and C_{12} with temperature. The result is also verified by literature⁴. If body is elongated in axial direction then its dimension reduces in the transverse direction. This indicates that if interaction forces among the atoms reduce with temperature along axial direction then it will enhance with temperature in the transverse direction. Due to this reason, C_{44} is found to increase with temperature.

Table 2 represents that the quantities Y , B , G , μ , λ and σ are found to decrease with temperature in AuRE intermetallics. The reduction in these quantities with temperature is due to decay in SOECs with temperature. This confirms the decay in average potential energy and ionic nature of bond among the atoms of AuRE intermetallics at high temperature. The reduction in σ

Table 2 – Second order elastic constants (SOECs), bulk modulus (B), Young's modulus (Y), shear modulus (G), Lamé modulus (λ) and Poisson ratio (σ) of AuRE compounds at different temperatures.

AuRE ↓	T [K]	C_{11} (GPa)	C_{12} (GPa)	C_{44} (GPa)	Y (GPa)	B (GPa)	G (GPa)	λ (GPa)	σ
AuSm	300	60.7	42.6	42.9	56.3	48.1	21.6	33.7	0.305
	450	59.8	41.8	42.3	55.7	47.4	21.3	33.1	0.304
	600	59.0	41.1	41.7	55.1	46.6	21.1	32.5	0.303
	750	58.2	40.4	41.1	54.5	45.9	20.9	31.9	0.302
	900	57.4	39.6	40.5	53.9	45.1	20.7	31.3	0.301
AuTb	300	66.1	45.3	45.7	61.7	51.7	23.7	35.9	0.301
	450	65.3	44.5	45.2	61.2	50.9	23.5	35.3	0.299
	600	64.5	43.7	44.6	60.6	50.1	23.3	34.6	0.298
	750	63.6	43.0	44.0	60.0	49.4	23.2	33.9	0.297
	900	62.8	42.2	43.4	59.4	48.5	22.9	33.3	0.296
AuHo	300	70.9	47.6	48.2	66.6	54.9	25.7	37.8	0.298
	450	70.1	46.8	47.6	66.0	54.0	25.5	37.0	0.296
	600	69.3	45.9	47.0	65.5	53.2	25.3	36.3	0.295
	750	68.4	45.1	46.4	64.9	56.5	25.1	35.1	0.293
	900	67.6	44.3	45.9	64.4	51.5	24.9	34.9	0.292
AuTm	300	93.8	50.3	52.3	89.4	64.2	35.2	40.7	0.268
	450	92.9	49.3	52.3	89.2	63.2	35.2	39.7	0.265
	600	92.0	48.2	52.2	89.1	62.2	35.3	38.7	0.261
	750	91.1	47.2	52.1	88.9	61.2	35.3	37.6	0.258
	900	90.2	46.1	52.1	88.7	60.2	35.4	36.6	0.254

with temperature also confirms that chosen intermetallics have comparatively large ionic bond character at high temperature. The decay of B with temperature indicates that compressibility of AuRE intermetallics increases with temperature. The quantities Y , B , G , λ and σ with temperature of AuRE intermetallics varies in similar way as AgRE (RE=Tb, Dy, Ho, Er, Tm) intermetallics reported elsewhere¹⁶.

The ultrasonic velocities are evaluated with the help of second order elastic constants and densities using Eq. (11) for ultrasonic wave propagation along $\langle 100 \rangle$ and $\langle 111 \rangle$ crystallographic directions. The calculated ultrasonic velocities are shown in Table 3. Debye average velocity (V_D) are calculated using Eqs. (12) which are also shown in Table 3. The estimated V_D is utilized for the calculation of Debye temperature (T_D).

The ultrasonic velocity defines the anisotropic characteristic of crystalline material as it is related to the second order/stiffness constants of the material. The estimated ultrasonic velocities of AuTb, AuHo and AuTm are quite similar to values reported elsewhere at 300K¹. Hence, our calculated velocities of chosen

intermetallics are justified. The ultrasonic velocities (V_L and V_S) are found to vary not only with temperature but also with the direction of propagation of ultrasonic wave. The temperature dependent V_L and V_S of AuRE materials for wave propagation along $\langle 100 \rangle$ direction are found to resemble the variation of C_{11} and C_{44} with temperature. At constant temperature, the variation of ultrasonic velocities with material (AuSm to AuTm) for $\langle 100 \rangle$ direction of wave propagation are found to be governed by density. The ultrasonic velocities along $\langle 111 \rangle$ direction have been found to decrease with temperature while increase with material. The combined effect of second order elastic constants is the dominating factor towards the ultrasonic velocities in AuRE intermetallics for $\langle 111 \rangle$ direction of wave propagation.

Therefore, the study of ultrasonic velocity in AuRE with temperature and direction provides the information about variation trend of elastic constants, lattice parameter and density of the material. The longitudinal ultrasonic velocities are obtained larger than that of shear ultrasonic velocity for each direction of propagation because stiffness constant C_{11} is found

Table 3 – The velocities of ultrasonic wave (10^3m/sec) of AuRE intermetallics for wave propagation along [100] and [111] direction at different temperatures

Direction → AuRE ↓	T [K]	<100>			<111>		
		V_L	V_S	V_D	V_L	V_S	V_D
AuSm	300	2.235	1.879	1.972	2.951	1.293	1.443
	450	2.224	1.869	1.962	2.935	1.288	1.438
	600	2.213	1.859	1.951	2.918	1.284	1.432
	750	2.201	1.849	1.942	2.901	1.279	1.427
	900	2.190	1.839	1.931	2.884	1.274	1.421
AuTb	300	2.262	1.882	1.980	2.960	1.310	1.461
	450	2.252	1.873	1.971	2.945	1.306	1.456
	600	2.241	1.864	1.962	2.930	1.302	1.452
	750	2.231	1.855	1.952	2.914	1.298	1.448
	900	2.220	1.846	1.943	2.898	1.295	1.443
AuHo	300	2.290	1.886	1.989	2.973	1.327	1.479
	450	2.280	1.879	1.980	2.958	1.324	1.476
	600	2.271	1.871	1.972	2.944	1.321	1.472
	750	2.261	1.861	1.962	2.929	1.318	1.469
	900	2.251	1.855	1.955	2.923	1.314	1.465
AuTm	300	2.591	1.935	2.054	3.103	1.511	1.678
	450	2.583	1.937	2.055	3.096	1.515	1.681
	600	2.575	1.939	2.056	3.089	1.518	1.685
	750	2.567	1.942	2.057	3.082	1.522	1.688
	900	2.559	1.945	2.058	3.075	1.525	1.691

greater than C_{12} or C_{44} for all the intermetallics under study. The estimated values of Debye temperature (T_D) of AuSm, AuTb, AuHo and AuTm are 204K, 207K, 210 K and 221 K, respectively. Since, the Debye average velocity is maxima for AuTm among selected intermetallics, therefore Debye temperature is found large for AuTm intermetallic. The ultrasonic velocities at different temperature of AuRE intermetallics along <100> and <111> directions varies from AuSm to AuTm as AgRE (RE=Tb, Dy, Ho, Er, Tm) intermetallics¹⁶.

The thermal expansion coefficient (α) is a thermo-physical property of materials which defines the melting point under the effect of external stimuli. Figure 1 reveals that the thermal expansion coefficient (α) decreases while melting point increases for AuRE intermetallics as RE varies from Sm to Tm. The thermal expansion coefficient is inversely proportional to the density (Eq. 14) which is received to increase from AuSm to AuTm, therefore thermal expansion coefficient is obtained to decrease respectively. Since, melting temperature has inverse relationship with thermal expansion coefficient, hence, its nature is found to have opposite behavior

with respect to thermal expansion coefficient under the variation of rare earth element in AuRE intermetallics (Fig. 1).

Conclusion

On the basis of above discussion, we conclude that our potential model theory for evaluation of second order elastic constants is justified for AuRE intermetallics. The elastic moduli and density of AuRE are found to enhance with decay in temperature and variation of RE from Sm to Tm. This feature is found to be evinced by change in lattice parameter with temperature and material. The ultrasonic velocities in chosen intermetallics are found to be quantitatively governed by second order elastic constants, direction of propagation and temperature. The intermetallic AuTm is found to have high elastic constant, mechanical strength and melting point among the chosen AuRE intermetallics. The analysis of obtained results also reveals that these intermetallics possess lower elastic constant, mechanical strength, ultrasonic velocity and melting point in comparison to intermetallics formed

by chosen rare earth element with Zn, Cu and Ag. Hence, the obtained results provide a good understanding of elastic, mechanical, thermal and ultrasonic properties of chosen rare-earth intermetallics that may be used for further investigation and also in material manufacturing industries.

Acknowledgement

Authors express their high gratitude to Prof. R.R. Yadav, University of Allahabad and Prof. Devraj Singh, V.B.S. Purvanchal University, Jaunpur for their valuable discussion and support during the course of manuscript preparation.

References

- Ahmad S., Shafiq M., Ahmad R., Jalali-Asadabadi S. and Ahmad I., Strongly correlated intermetallic rare-earth monoaurides (Ln-Au): Ab-initio study. *J. Rare Earths*. **36**, (2018) 1106.
- Liu L., Xiaozhi W., Weiguo L., Wang R. and Liu Q., High temperature and pressure effects on the elastic properties of B2 intermetallics AgRE. *Open Phys*. **13**, (2015) 142-150.
- Singh R.P., Singh V.K., Singh R.K. and Rajagopalan M., Elastic, Acoustical and Electronic Behaviour of the RM (R = Dy, Ho, Er; M=Cu, Zn) Compounds. *American J. of Cond. Matt. Phys*. **3**(5), (2013) 123-132.
- Russell A.M., Ductility in Intermetallic Compounds. *Adv. Engg. Mat.*, **5**, (2003) 629-639.
- Russell A.M., Zhang Z., Lograsso T.A., Lo C. H. C., Pecharsky A. O., Morris J.R., Ye Y.Y., Gschneidner Jr K.A. and Slager A. J., Mechanical properties of single crystal YAg. *Acta Mater*. **52**, (2004) 4033-4040.
- Buschow K. H. J. and Vucht van J. H. N., Systemetic Arrangement of the Binary Rare-Earth-Aluminium SYSTEMS. *Philips Res. Repts*. **22**, (1967) 233-245.
- Dong H.Q., Tao X.M., Laurila T. and Paulasto-Kröcke M., Thermodynamic assessment of Au-Ho and Au-Tm binary systems. *Calphad*. **37**, (2012) 87-93.
- Ahmad S., Ahmad R., Jalali-Asadabadi S. and Ahmad I., First principle studies of electronic and magnetic properties of Lanthanide-Gold (RAu) binary intermetallics. *J. Magn. Magn. Mater*. **422**, (2017) 458-463.
- Brugger K., Thermodynamics definition of Higher Order Elastic coefficients, *Phys. Rev*. **133**(6A), (1964) A1611.
- Singhal R. L., "Solid state physics", *Kedar Nath Ram Nath & Co. Publishers*, Meerut, India, **73**, (2003).
- Yadav R. R. and Pandey D. K., Size dependent acoustical properties of bcc metal, *Acta Phy. Pol. A* **107**, (2005) 933-946.
- Yadav C .P., Pandey D .K. and Singh D., Elastic and Ultrasonic Studies on RM (R=Tb, Dy, Ho, Tm; M=Zn, Cu) Compounds. *Z. Naturforsch. A* **74**, (2019) 1123-1130.
- Khan A., Yadav C .P., Pandey D .K., Singh D. and Singh D., Elastic and thermo-acoustic study of YM intermetallics. *J. Pure Appl. Ultrasonic*. **41**, (2019) 1-8.
- Pandey D. K. and Yadav C. P., Thermophysical and ultrasonic properties of GdCu under the effect of temperature and pressure. *Phase transitions*. **93**(3), (2020) 338-349.
- Bala J., Singh D., Pandey D. K. and Yadav C. P., Mechanical and thermophysical properties of ScM (M: Ru, Rh, Pd, Ag) intermetallics. *Int. J. Thermophysic*. **41**, (2020) 46.
- Khan M. A., Kumar M., Yadav C. P. and Pandey D. K., Mechanical, thermal and ultrasonic properties of AgRE intermetallics at different temperatures. *Phase Transitions*. **95**(2), (2022) 131-142.
- Moakafi M., Khenata R., Bouhemadou A., Semari F., Reshak A. H. and Rabah M., Elastic, electronic and optical properties of cubic antiperovskites SbNCa_3 and BiNCa_3 , *Comput. Mat. Sci*. **46**, (2009) 1051-1057.
- Pandey D.K. and Pandey S., in *Acoustic Waves: Ultrasonic: a technique of material characterization*, Eds: Don W. Dissanayake, Scio Publisher, *Sciyo Croatia*, (2010) 397-430.
- Pillai S.O., in *Solid State physics: Crystal physics*, 7th Ed. *New Age International Publisher*, (2005) 100- 111.